

Determinant Of Initial Return in Companies Sector Consumer Cyclical On IDX

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Abstract: Growing companies need funds to finance their business activities. Funds can be obtained by offering shares through the capital market or listing on the stock exchange. Companies that want to sell their shares on the secondary market or stock exchange must make a public offering on the primary market, called an Initial Public Offering (IPO). IPO is the cheapest price if you want to invest, because IPO companies have large growth potential. An IPO phenomenon that often occurs is the emergence of differences in share prices in the primary market and secondary market. Price differences (initial returns) can cause profits or losses for companies and investors. The consumer cyclical sector is the sector that dominates trading in the secondary market. The aim of this research is to analyze the influence of ROA, EPS, PER, DER, company size, company age, auditor's reputation, and underwriter's reputation and analyze the variables that determine initial returns in consumer cyclicals sector companies on the IDX using statistical analysis with the SPSS 26 program. A sample of 49 customer cyclicals companies that met the criteria was obtained. The research results show that the determinant variable that influences initial returns in consumer cyclical companies is ROA. Meanwhile EPS, PER, DER, company size, company age, auditor reputation and underwriter reputation do not have a significant effect.

Keywords: IPO, initial return, consumer cyclicals, IDX.

INTRODUCTION

Growing companies need funds to finance their business activities. Funds can be obtained through loans from banks or other financial institutions. Companies can also issue bonds and offer shares through the capital market or listing on the stock exchange. Companies that sell their shares through the stock exchange have several stages, starting from the preparation stage, submitting a registration application, offering securities on the primary market and the final stage, namely listing securities on the secondary market (exchange).

Companies that want to sell their shares on the secondary market or stock exchange must make a public offering on the primary market, called an Initial Public Offering (IPO). IPO is the cheapest price if you want to invest, because IPO companies have large growth potential. An IPO phenomenon that often occurs is the emergence of differences in share prices in the primary market and secondary market. Price differences (initial returns) can cause profits or losses for companies and investors

Officially on January 25 2021 the Indonesian Stock Exchange using IDX Industrial Classification (IDX-IC), IDX-IC has 12 sectors whereas previously there were only 9 sectors. One of these sectors is Consumer Cyclical as reported by (CNN Indonesia, 2021). The consumer cyclical sector is the sector that dominates trading in the secondary market. Companies that will offer shares on the secondary market have an obligation to convey their business activities to the public through a prospectus. The prospectus contains financial report information and other information. This information can be a determining factor for investors to buy company shares.

The variable that is the determinant initial return in sector companies consumer cyclicals on the IDX can be seen from previous studies. Based on the results of research conducted by (Utami et al., 2020) it shows that ownership retention, company age, and underwriter reputation has a positive and significant influence on ICD in IPOs, where as financial leverage and company size has no effect on ICD in IPOs. The results of research conducted by (Tanoyo & Arfianti, 2022) show that financial leverage positive and significant effect on underpricing or initial return while ROA, company size, underwriter reputation, and auditors reputation negative and significant effect on underpricing or initial return. And research conducted by (Sianggaran & Swandari, 2023) shows that EPS has a positive and significant effect on IPO price or initial return while ROA, ROE, DER, PER, Trading Volume have no effect on IPO price or initial return.

The variables considered can influence the level initial return in this research using variables Return on Assets (ROA), Earnings Per Share (EPS), Price Earnings Ratio (PER), Debt Equity Ratio (DER), company size, company age, auditors reputation, and underwriter reputation. These variables are further used to reveal the influencing determinant variables initial return on sectors consumer cyclicals on BEI.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Signaling Theory

Signal theory is used to explain information in the form of positive signals or negative signals that is useful and can be utilized by companies and investors. The signal theory obtained during an IPO can be used by investors to determine the condition of the company. Titman and Trueman (1986) and Datar, Feltham, and Hughes (1991) in (Scott, 2020: 503) developed a model where audit quality is used as a signal that produces information that is useful in estimating the value of companies conducting an IPO.

Prospectus

The prospectus contains investment objectives, strategy, company performance, management, and other matters related to the company. The preparation of the prospectus is guided by the Board of Commissioners of the Financial Services Authority (OJK), (2017) Number 8/POJK.04/2017 concerning the Form and Content of the Prospectus and Abridged Prospectus for the Context of a Public Offering of Equity Securities. The Prospectus and Abridged Prospectus must be prepared in such a way that it is clear and communicative.

Initial Return

According to (Hartono, 2016:37) initial return is the return from assets from the time the initial offering begins to be purchased on the primary market until it is first registered on the secondary market. Initial return is the profit obtained by shareholders because the difference between the price of shares purchased in the primary market is smaller and the selling price of the relevant shares in the secondary market, which is often called underpricing where the share price at the time of the IPO is significantly lower than the initial price on the secondary market. Initial Return occurs when the share value at the time of the initial public offering is lower than the secondary market and there is a positive difference in share value (Sunarko & Rasyid, 2019:162)

Return On Assets (ROA)

ROA according to (Kasmir, 2012:201) is a ratio that shows the results (return) on the number of assets used in the company. In addition, ROA provides a better measure of a company's profitability because it shows management's effectiveness in using assets to generate income. According to (Brigham & Houston, 2010: 107) profitability ratios are a group of ratios that show the combined effects of liquidity, asset management and debt on operating results. A high profitability ratio shows the company's ability to fulfill its obligations and shows the company's ability to go concern.

Earnings Per Share (EPS)

EPS or profit per share is a form of profit given to shareholders from each share owned (Fahmi, 2012:96). According to (Tambunan, 2013:2016) EPS is the return per share obtained from dividing net profit by the number of shares outstanding. Investors who invest in the capital market need to be careful in making decisions related to shares. Accurate stock assessment can minimize risks so that you don't make mistakes in decision making. Therefore, investors need to analyze the company's financial condition to make decisions about investing in shares

Price Earnings Ratio (PER)

(Tandelilin, 2010:320) explains "PER is the ratio or comparison between share price and company earnings". Meanwhile, according to (Hartono, 2016: 204), "PER shows the ratio of share price to earnings, where this ratio shows how much investors value the price of shares against the multiple of earnings." This is different from the opinion of (Halim, 2005:10) which states that this ratio describes the investor's willingness to pay a certain amount for every rupiah of company profit. PER is a comparison of the share price per share with earnings per share. The use of PER itself is used to determine investor capital in order to obtain earnings from the company. A low PER value has its own attraction for investors.

Debt Equity Ratio (DER)

According to (Darsono & Ashari, 2010:54-55) DER is a leverage or solvency ratio. The solvency ratio is a ratio to determine a company's ability to pay its obligations if the company is liquidated. This ratio is also called the leverage ratio, which assesses the company's limits in borrowing money. This ratio shows the comparison of debt and capital. This ratio is an important ratio because it is related to the issue of trading on equity, which can have a positive and negative influence on the profitability of own capital and the company.

Company Size

According to (Brigham et al., 2011: 14) company size is the size of the company which can be classified based on various ways, including the size of income, total assets and total equity. Company size is a scale of measurement seen from the total assets of a company or organization that combines and organizes various resources with the aim of producing goods or services for sale. The influence of company size on company value is supported by signaling theory

Company Age

The age of the company shows how long the company is able to survive and is proof that the company is able to compete and can take advantage of business opportunities that exist in the economy (Astuti & Djamaluddin, 2021:33). The age of a company reflects the company's ability to survive in a highly competitive business environment. The longer a business has been around, the more likely it is to survive and develop (Sunarko & Rasyid, 2019). The age of the company

can show the ability to overcome difficulties and obstacles that can threaten the life of the company and shows the company's ability to take opportunities in its environment to develop the business.

Auditors Reputation

The financial report submitted by the company that will conduct an IPO to BAPEPAM must be a financial report that has been audited by an independent auditor to provide confidence, especially to potential investors, regarding the veracity of the financial report. The use of professional advisors (auditors and underwriters who have a high reputation) can be used as a sign or indication of the quality of the issuing company. By using professional and qualified advisors, issuers will reduce the opportunity to cheat in presenting inaccurate information to the market. So, companies conducting an IPO will choose a KAP that has a good reputation. Higher audit quality improves the quality of information disclosure, and high quality disclosure reduces information imbalance by expanding the scope of investors' public information and bringing private information to the public (Daryaei et al., 2022:139-141)

Underwriters Reputation

A company that decides to IPO will use the services of a securities company that acts as an underwriter or underwriter. Underwriters play an important role in determining share prices in initial offerings (IPO). Before placing shares, the underwriter helps the company to prepare a prospectus and then provides an appropriate assessment for determining the share price in the primary market. An experienced and reputable underwriter will be able to organize an IPO professionally and provide better service to issuers because they know more about current market conditions. Underwriters who have a high reputation will have more confidence in the success of the shares being offered in being absorbed by the market and a good underwriter's reputation will provide a good signal to the market (Utomo & Kurniasih, 2020: 119).

Research Hypothesis Development

Regarding initial returns, the hypothesis that will be used in this research is

- H₁: ROA has a significant effect on Initial Return
- H₂: EPS has a significant effect on Initial Return
- H₃: PER has a significant effect on Initial Return
- H₄: DER has a significant effect on Initial Return
- H₅: Company size has a significant effect on Initial Return
- H₆: Company age has a significant effect on Initial Return
- H₇: Auditors reputation has a significant effect on Initial Return
- H₈: Underwriters reputation has a significant effect on Initial Return

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHODS

The research study used in this research is an explanatory study. Explanatory study is to explain a situation, usually in the form of a cause and effect relationship preceded by a survey or experimental design. The data used in this research is sourced from data secondary issues published and stated in the prospectus company. The company prospectus is taken from the official website of each issuer or other sources.

The population in this research is all companies in the consumer cyclicals sector that conducted an Initial Public Offering (IPO) that listed their shares on the IDX in 2018-2023. Based on data from the IDX via the website www.idx.co.id and the websites of each company, a population of 63 companies (issuers) was obtained. The sample in this study was selected using a purposive sampling method, namely with the following criteria:

1. Consumer cyclicals companies whose IPO closing price experiences an increase from the offering price,
2. Consumer cyclical companies that IPO have complete data.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data used in this research is secondary data obtained from financial reports (annual reports) on companies that conducted Initial Public Offerings (IPOs) listed on the IDX for the 2018-2023 period. Data source via site www.idx.co.id and the websites of each company. Sample selection was carried out using the purposive sampling method. The sample selection procedure in this research can be seen in table 1 below.

Table 1. Sample Selection Criteria

No	Sample Criteria	Amount
1	Consumer cyclicals sector companies that will IPO on the IDX in 2018-2023	63
2	Consumer cyclicals companies that IPO do not experience an increase in their offering price	(8)
3	Consumer cyclicals companies that IPO do not have complete data (because shares are suspended)	(6)
Sample in research		49

Table 1 shows the total number of companies during the period 2018 to 2023. This resulted in a sample of 49 customer cyclical companies that met the criteria.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics provide an overview or description of data seen from the average value (mean), standard deviation, variance, maximum, minimum, sum, range, kurtosis and skewness or skewness of the distribution (Ghozali, 2018). From the results of this descriptive statistical analysis, it can provide an overview of conclusions from the data analysis. The results of descriptive statistics with the help of the SPSS version 26 computer application program are presented in the following table:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics Test Results

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
IR	49	0.45	70.00	34.7602	24.05472
ROA	49	-10.21	36.42	4.9027	7.43912
EPS	49	-372575.66	599531.07	20977.3529	136311.19495
PER	49	-41.00	349.94	39.3133	78.79643
DER	49	3.85	7129.58	320.0322	1131.45751
SIZE	49	13523	6759546	675648.65	1136361.185
AGE	49	1	35	12.94	8.955
RA	49	0	1	.12	.331
RU	49	0	1	.22	.422
Valid N (listwise)	49				

Based on table 2 above, it shows the minimum, maximum, average values (mean) and standard deviation of a total of 49 sample sector companies consumer cyclicals which conducted an IPO on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2018-2023 period. Data from Initial Return has an average of 34%. This shows that the company estimates the initial share price too low, reaching 34% on average compared to the price sold on the secondary market. Issuers who experience Initial Return the highest was 70% for the companies Esta Multi Usaha Tbk, DMS Propertindo Tbk, Citra Putra Realty Tbk, and Arkadia Digital Media Tbk while Initial Return the lowest was experienced by Sarimelati Kencana Tbk, namely 0.45%.

Return on Assets (ROA) shows the company's ability to generate net profits based on the level of assets in the last financial report before conducting the IPO. Based on data from 49 sample sector companies consumer cyclicals, obtained an average ROA of 4%. This shows that on average issuers earn a net profit of 4% compared to total assets in

the last report before the IPO. The lowest ROA was -10% obtained by Hotel Fitra International Tbk and the highest ROA was obtained by Lima Dua Lima Tiga Tbk, reaching 36%.

Earnings Per Share (EPS) from 49 sample companies obtained an average of 20,977. This average value shows that on average the company's profits in generating dividends in companies conducting IPOs from 2018 to 2023 are able to generate dividends per share of IDR. 20,977. The minimum EPS value obtained was -Rp 372,575 obtained by Menteng Heritage Realty Tbk. The maximum EPS value obtained was IDR 599,531 obtained by Putra Mandiri Jembar Tbk.

Price Earnings Ratio (PER) from 49 sample companies obtained an average of 39x. This average value shows that on average the price of a share is based on the company's ability to generate profits. Companies that carry out an IPO in 2018 to 2023 are able to generate a price per share of 39 times the price it should be. The minimum PER value obtained was -41x obtained by Multitrend Indo Tbk. The maximum PER value obtained was 349x obtained by Surya Permata Andalan Tbk.

Debt Equity Ratio (DER) has an average DER of 320%. This shows that before the initial share offering, 49 sample companies had total debt of up to 3.2 times the company's own capital. This condition illustrates that companies in their corporate funding policies tend to use debt from third parties rather than using their own capital. It is possible that the high DER is due to the company developing its business so that before offering shares to the public, the company borrows from third parties. The lowest DER value obtained was 3.85% owned by Surya Permata Andalan Tbk, while the highest DER was owned by Net Visi Media Tbk, namely 7.129%.

Other information from 49 sample sector consumer cyclicals who conducted an IPO. The average value of company size is measured based on the total asset value. The average value of total assets is 675,648,650,000 with a minimum size value of 13,523,000,000, namely Arkadia Digital Media Tbk and the largest company size is the Nusantara Sejahtera Raya Tbk company, namely 6,759,546,000,000. The age variable is based on the average age of companies conducting an IPO of 12 years. The lowest age is 1 year, namely Lima Dua Lima Tiga Tbk, while the maximum age is 35 years, namely Nusantara Sejahtera Raya Tbk.

Data on companies that have reputable or categorized auditors The Big Four namely a number of 6 companies and companies that are not included in the category The Big Four reputable auditors, namely 43 companies. This shows that it is not included in the category The Big Four reputable auditors have dominated.

Meanwhile, data on companies that have an underwriter reputation or are included in the category The Big Ten namely a number of 11 companies and companies that are not included in the category The Big Ten Reputable underwriters, namely 38 companies. This shows that it does not fall into the category The Big Ten Reputable underwriters have dominated

Normality Test Results

The normality test is used to test whether the data in a regression model is normally distributed or not. A good regression model is where the data is distributed normally or close to normal. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results from this research are presented in Table 3 as follows:

Table 3. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test Results

		Unstandardized Residual
N		49
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0.0000000
	Std. Deviation	21.12712423
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.084
	Positive	0.079
	Negative	-0.084
Test Statistic		0.084
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.200 ^{c,d}

Based on Table 3, the results of normality testing using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, value Asymp. Sign (2-tailed) is 0.200 which means that the value Asymp. Sign (2-tailed) > 0.05, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test Results

The multicollinearity test aims to find out whether in the multiple regression model there is a correlation between the independent variables or not. Symptoms of multicollinearity can be identified by looking at the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value. The results of the multicollinearity test can be seen in table 4 as follows:

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	ROA	0.861	1.161
	EPS	0.833	1.200
	PER	0.842	1.188
	DER	0.829	1.207
	SIZE	0.470	2.126
	AGE	0.693	1.443
	RA	0.617	1.622
	RU	0.627	1.596

Based on Table 4.4, it shows the results of the multicollinearity test for each independent variable with values tolerance > 0.10 or VIF < 10, this proves that the research data is free from symptoms of multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test Results

This test aims to find out whether in the regression model there is an inequality in the residual variance between one another. A good regression model that meets the requirements for testing is data that does not contain heteroscedasticity. To test whether there is a problem with heteroscedasticity in the regression, it can be seen from the probability value of the variable. The results of heteroscedasticity testing in this study can be seen in Table 5 as follows:

Table 5. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	25.084	3.554		7.059	0.000
	ROA	-0.351	0.228	-0.238	-1.539	0.132
	EPS	-1.089E-5	0.000	-0.136	-0.861	0.394
	PER	-0.030	0.022	-0.215	-1.372	0.178
	DER	-0.001	0.002	-0.133	-0.840	0.406
	SIZE	3.961E-8	0.000	0.004	0.020	0.984
	AGE	-0.197	0.211	-0.162	-0.935	0.355
	RA	5.633	6.051	0.170	0.931	0.357
	RU	-8.140	4.716	-0.314	-1.726	0.092

Based on Table 5, it can be seen that the significance value of each independent variable shows a value greater than 0.05. It can be concluded that heteroscedasticity did not occur in this study.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis is used to determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The results of regression calculations using the SPSS 26 program can be seen in Table 6 as follows:

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	43.136	7.543		5.719	0.000
	ROA	-1.150	0.484	-0.356	-2.377	0.022
	EPS	7.099E-7	0.000	0.004	0.026	0.979
	PER	0.043	0.046	0.142	0.939	0.353
	DER	0.000	0.003	0.021	0.137	0.892
	SIZE	2.016E-6	0.000	0.095	0.470	0.641
	AGE	-0.497	0.448	-0.185	-1.108	0.274
	RA	-14.896	12.844	-0.205	-1.160	0.253
	RU	10.187	10.010	0.179	1.018	0.315

Based on Table 6, the following equation is obtained for multiple linear regression analysis in the research, namely:

$$Y = 43.136 - 1.150 \text{ ROA} + 7.099\text{E} - 7\text{EPS} + 0.043\text{PER} + 0.000\text{DER} + 2.016\text{E} - 6\text{SIZE} - 0.497\text{AGE} - 14.896\text{RA} + 10.187 \text{RU} + \varepsilon$$

Dimana:

Y	: Initial Return
ROA	: Return on Assets
EPS	: Earnings Per Share
PER	: Price Earnings Ratio
DER	: Debt Equity Ratio
SIZE	: Company Size
AGE	: Company Age
RA	: Auditors Reputation
RU	: Underwriters Reputation
ε	: error term

Results of the Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 7. Results of Determination Coefficient (R^2)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	0.478 ^a	0.229	0.074	23.14361

Based on Table 7, it shows the results of testing the coefficient of determination which aims to see how much the independent variable is able to explain the dependent variable. Mark Adjusted R-Square amounting to 0.074 or 7.4% which shows that the independent variables namely ROA, EPS, PER, DER, SIZE, AGE, RA, and RU are able to explain the dependent variable namely Initial Return 7.4% and 92.6% were influenced by other factors outside the variables used in this research.

Partial Test Results (t Test)

The t test is used to determine whether there is a linear influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The t table value is obtained from $df = nk - 1 = 49 - 8 - 1 = 40$, the t table is 2.021. The partial test results can be seen in Table 8 as follows: 34

Table 8. t test results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	43.136	7.543		5.719	0.000
	ROA	-1.150	0.484	-0.356	-2.377	0.022
	EPS	7.099E-7	0.000	0.004	0.026	0.979
	PER	0.043	0.046	0.142	0.939	0.353
	DER	0.000	0.003	0.021	0.137	0.892
	SIZE	2.016E-6	0.000	0.095	0.470	0.641
	AGE	-0.497	0.448	-0.185	-1.108	0.274
	RA	-14.896	12.844	-0.205	-1.160	0.253
	RU	10.187	10.010	0.179	1.018	0.315

Table 8 shows the calculated t value and significance for each variable:

1. ROA test results show a significance of $0.022 < 0.05$ and a t-count value of $2.377 > t$ table of 2.021. This explains that variable Return on Assets (ROA) has a significant effect on Initial Return with hypothesis H_0 rejected as well H_1 accepted.
2. EPS test results show a significance of $0.979 > 0.05$ and a t-count value of $0.026 < t$ table of 2.021. This explains that variable Earnings Per Share (EPS) has no significant effect on Initial Return with hypothesis H_0 accepted as well H_2 rejected.
3. PER test results show a significance of $0.353 > 0.05$ and a t-count value of $0.939 < t$ table of 2.021. This explains that variable Price Earnings Ratio (PER) has no significant effect on Initial Return with hypothesis H_0 accepted as well H_3 rejected.
4. DER test results show a significance of $0.892 > 0.05$ and a t-count value 35 of $0.137 < t$ table of 2.021. This explains that variable Debt Equity Ratio (DER) has no significant effect on Initial Return with hypothesis H_0 accepted as well H_4 rejected.

5. SIZE test results show a significance of $0.641 > 0.05$ and a t value of $0.470 < t$ table of 2.021. This explains that the Company Size variable does not have a significant effect on Initial Return with hypothesis H_0 accepted as well H_5 rejected.

6. The AGE test results show a significance of $0.274 > 0.05$ and a t value of $1.108 < t$ table of 2.021. This explains that the Company Age variable does not have a significant effect on Initial Return with hypothesis H_0 accepted as well H_6 rejected.

7. The RA test results show a significance of $0.253 > 0.05$ and a t-count value of $1.160 < t$ table of 2.021. This explains the Auditors Reputation variable has no significant effect on Initial Return with hypothesis H_0 accepted as well H_7 rejected.

8. The RU test results show a significance of $0.315 > 0.05$ and a t-count value of $1.018 < t$ table of 2.021. This explains the Underwriters Reputation variable has no significant effect on Initial Return with hypothesis H_0 accepted as well H_8 rejected.

Discussion

Effect of Return on Assets (ROA) to Initial Return in sector companies consumer cyclicals on BEI

The test results using the SPSS program show that the ROA variable is known to have a negative coefficient value of -1.150 and is significant. With a significance of $0.022 < 0.05$ and a t-count value of $2.377 > t$ table of 2.021. The t test value shows that the ROA variable has a significant effect in a negative direction Initial Return in line with research conducted by (Yadav et al., 2023) and (Zuliardi & Witiastuti, 2020). This shows that the lower the ROA, investors will be willing to buy their first shares at a higher price. Because investors will better assess the company's performance in generating future profits.

Effect of Earnings Per Share (EPS) to Initial Return in sector companies consumer cyclicals on BEI

The test results show that the EPS variable is known to have a positive coefficient value of $7.099E-7$ and is not significant. The EPS significance value is $0.979 > 0.05$ and the t-calculated value is $0.026 < t$ table of 2.021. The t test value shows that the EPS variable has no significant effect on Initial Return in line with research conducted by (Sunarko & Rasyid, 2019). This can happen because investors involved in investment activities are long-term investors. Investors do not only want short-term profits or investors whose goal is only to obtain initial returns, but also long-term company performance. Thus, the high or low EPS value is not the main factor for investors to invest in a company so it does not affect the low valuation.

Effect of Price Earnings Ratio (PER) to Initial Return in sector companies consumer cyclicals on BEI

The test results showed that the PER variable was found to have a positive coefficient value of 0.043 and was not significant. The significance value of PER is $0.353 > 0.05$ and the t-count value is $0.939 < t$ table of 2.021. The t test value shows that the variable PER has no significant effect on Initial Return in line with research conducted by (Ali et al., 2020). The higher a share PER will be directly proportional to the high expected net profit growth. Shares with a high PER value are also often considered expensive shares if the company's profits decline. However, shares with a low PER are not always bad shares, and vice versa. Therefore, the high or low PER is not a determining factor for an investor to invest.

Effect of Debt Equity Ratio (DER) to Initial Return in sector companies consumer cyclicals on BEI

The test results show that the DER variable is known to have a positive coefficient value of 0.000 and is not significant. The significance value of DER is $0.892 > 0.05$ and the t-count value is $0.137 < t$ table of 2.021. The t test value shows that the DER variable has no significant effect on Initial Return in line with research conducted by (Utami et al., 2020). A positive DER is not an influencing factor for investors who want to invest. It's just that the company wants to display a good reputation in managing its debt. Because however investors in the future see how much the company can use its debt for the company's operational costs, if the company succeeds in using debt for operational cost then this will provide a positive signal for investors in the future to invest their capital, and the share price will rise, and vice versa if If a company fails to utilize debt, it will give a negative signal to investors.

Effect of Company Size to Initial Return in sector companies consumer cyclicals on BEI

The test results show that the Company Size variable is known to have a positive coefficient value of $2.016E-6$ and is not significant. The significance value of Company Size is $0.641 > 0.05$ and the t-count value is $0.470 < t$ table of 2.021. The t test value shows that the Company Size variable has no significant effect on Initial Return in line with research conducted by (Utami et al., 2020). This explains that the size of the company cannot provide any signal from investors, meaning that investors do not assess the size of the company in making investment decisions so that it does not have an impact on the level of investment.initial return. So it can be concluded that the findings can be caused by investors assessing company performance more than company size.

Effect of Company Age to Initial Return in sector companies consumer cyclicals on BEI

The test results showed that the Company Age variable was found to have a negative coefficient of -0.497 and was not significant. The significance value of Company Age is $0.274 > 0.05$ and the t-count value is $1.108 < t$ table of 2.021. The t test value shows that the Company Age variable has no significant effect on Initial Return in line with research

conducted by (Rada & Marsoem, 2020). This explains that in a business world that is synonymous with competition, young companies do not necessarily have worse performance or prospects than companies that have been around for a long time. And the age of the company cannot guarantee that the company is a company that has a healthy financial condition or company performance.

Effect of Auditors Reputation to Initial Return in sector companies consumer cyclicals on BEI

The test results showed that the Auditors Reputation variable It is known to have a negative coefficient value of -14.896 and is not significant. Auditors Reputation significance value of $0.253 > 0.05$ and the t-count value of $1.160 < t$ table of 2.021 . The t test value shows that the Auditors Reputation variable does not have a significant effect on Initial Return in line with research conducted by (Desiyanti et al., 2023). This may be caused by a lack of investor confidence in the auditor's report. The information provided by auditor services at the time of the IPO must reflect the company's credibility. If auditors fail to provide accurate information in a company's financial statements, investor confidence may be reduced, even when auditors affiliated with the Big4 are used.

Effect of Reputation Underwriters to Initial Return in sector companies consumer cyclicals on BEI

The test results showed that the Underwriters Reputation variable is known to have a positive coefficient value of 10.187 and is not significant. Underwriters Reputation significance value of $0.315 > 0.05$ and the t-count value of $1.018 < t$ table of 2.021 . The t test value shows that the Underwriters Reputation variable does not have a significant effect on Initial Return in line with research conducted by (Oktavia, 2019). This happens because a group of investors can obtain more information about the prospects of the issuing company without paying attention to the share price calculated by the underwriter

CONCLUSION

Conclusions obtained in research regarding determinants initial return at the company consumer cyclical on the IDX, it can be concluded that:

1. Analysis of the influence of ROA, EPS, PER, DER, company size, company age, auditors reputation, and underwriters reputation to initial return, are as follows:
 - a. The first hypothesis (H_1) was accepted, it was found that Return on Assets (ROA) has a significant negative effect on Initial Return
 - b. The second hypothesis (H_2) was rejected, it was found that Earnings Per Share (EPS) has no effect on Initial Return.
 - c. The third hypothesis (H_3) was rejected, it was found that Price Earnings Ratio (PER) has no effect on Initial Return.
 - d. The fourth hypothesis (H_4) was rejected, it was found that Debt Equity Ratio (DER) has no effect on Initial Return.
 - e. The fifth hypothesis (H_5) was rejected, it was found that company size had no effect on Initial Return.
 - f. The sixth hypothesis (H_6) was rejected, it was found that Company Age had no effect on Initial Return.
 - g. The seventh hypothesis (H_7) was rejected, it was found that Auditors Reputation has no effect on Initial Return.
 - h. The eighth hypothesis (H_8) was rejected, it was found that Underwriters Reputation has no effect on Initial Return.
2. Determinant variables that influence initial return in consumer cyclicals companies are Return on Assets (ROA)

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